

Supermarket Shopping with the help of Deep Learning

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Abstract. This study presents the development of an innovative system designed to facilitate the customers, especially elderly and people with disabilities, in their shopping experience. The proposed solution employs deep learning for product identification and obstacle detection in combination with a smartphone app that serves as the user interface. The solution offers functionalities such as product selection, shortest path calculation, automatic shopping list fulfillment and obstacle detection. The presented solution is part of a greater system that also consists of a self-propelled cart with indoor localization capabilities and a supermarket cloud platform.

1 Introduction

Supermarket shopping can be a time-consuming and cumbersome experience for customers and even more for elderly and individuals with disabilities. However, daily shopping in a supermarket can also be an opportunity for socialization and encouragement for independent living. In EU-27 there are 85 million people with disabilities, aged 16 and over living in private household according to the EU-SILC (EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions). Despite significant investments in outdoor infrastructure, less emphasis has been placed on the development of shared indoor infrastructure based on advances in information and communication technologies (ICT). To address this issue, we have developed an innovative system designed to facilitate shopping. The system is embedded in a self-propelled cart for people with disabilities. The system is comprised of four subsystems, the self-propelled cart with indoor localization capabilities, a cloud platform, a smartphone app and an embedded system attached to the shopping cart. The self-propelled cart and the cloud platform have been initially presented in [1]. In this paper the focus is on functionalities of the embedded system on the cart that are related to AI and the smartphone app that functions as the user interface of the system. The embedded system and the app support the list preparation, shortest route estimation, obstacle avoidance and automatic fulfillment of the list. The mobile app was developed with the accessibility standards as defined by the official Android Developer page[6]. The app serves as the primary user interface for the shopping cart, allowing users to create and manage shopping lists, check the fulfillment of the list during shopping and find a shortest route based on the selected products of the shopping list (figure 1). The app communicates with the supermarket cloud infrastructure to retrieve

product related information concerning availability, prices and location. The relevant AI functions of the system are the automatic list fulfillment with product object detection, the shortest route estimation and the obstacle detection. The above functions are performed on the embedded system and are visualized at the app.

Figure 1. Smartphone app screenshots

2 Methods

2.1 Automatic list fulfillment

The system employs deep learning for the object detection of the products during the automatic list fulfillment. Two cameras mounted on the shopping cart provide image input for a deep convolutional neural network (D-CNN) model. This camera-based object detection system is capable of identifying and categorizing items into predefined object classes that represent the products. As the products are identified by the model, the information is sent to the supermarket cloud platform and is then communicated to the app (figure 2). In order to create the object detection model an image dataset of 41 products was created. A total of 3,000 images were captured using the cameras mounted on the shopping cart. The images were taken

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from the two different camera positions on the cart and featured various combinations of products in the cart. This dataset was used to train the custom object detection model. During the preprocessing stage, the images were resized and padded to ensure they had appropriate dimensions for model retraining. The aspect ratios of the images were maintained to avoid distortion. Each product in the images was manually annotated using rectangular bounding boxes, with the corresponding class labels assigned to them. This task allows the model to learn both the location and the classification of the objects within the images. The MobileNet-SSD [7] was chosen as the network architecture for the object detection model. This architecture combines MobileNet for image feature extraction and the Single Shot Detector (SSD) for fast object localization. This architecture is primarily used in handheld and embedded devices for fast recognition. A pre-trained MobileNet-SSD model, initially trained on the COCO dataset[5] with 80 image classes, was modified to accommodate the custom dataset of 41 supermarket products. Transfer learning was employed to save training time by leveraging the pre-existing knowledge gained from the COCO dataset. The initial layers of the model, responsible for detecting low- and mid-level features such as edges and lines, were preserved. The last layer of the model was adjusted to accommodate the 41 product classes in the custom dataset. The PyTorch framework was used to retrain the MobileNet-SSD model on the custom dataset. The 3,000 images were divided into three sets: training, validation, and test sets. The model was trained using the training set and fine-tuned with the validation set to minimize the risk of overfitting. Finally, the test set was used to evaluate the model's performance on unseen data. During training, various hyperparameters such as learning rate, batch size, and the number of epochs were adjusted to optimize the model's performance. The accuracy metric was used to evaluate the model's ability to correctly detect and classify products in the images. Once the model was trained and evaluated, it was deployed on an NVIDIA Jetson Nano single board computer, by converting the model format from pytorch, to ONNX and finally to TensorRT engine. The NVIDIA Jetson Nano is a compact embedded system ideal for edge computing applications. The device received the image input from the two cameras mounted on the shopping cart and was able to perform real-time object detection at 15 frames per second.

Figure 2. Object detection camera for product identification

2.2 Shortest route estimation

The problem of routing in the supermarket, with target to find the shortest path for gathering all the products, can become very computationally demanding with the increase of the number of products. In the literature heuristic methods as genetic algorithms [2] are used instead of analytical ones as dynamic programming. In our solution we describe the problem as the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) [4]. The product collection process is modeled as a variant of the TSP, where products correspond to cities and the store's entry-exit corresponds to the first city. A network of nodes is created with fixed nodes at the beginning of the aisles and additional nodes at the locations of the products. The calculation of the shortest distances between products is performed using Dijkstra's algorithm [3]. Once the lengths of the shortest distances are calculated, we have a full correspondence with the TSP. To solve the TSP we use the simulated annealing method[8] (figure 3).

Figure 3. The nodes of the supermarket corridors (cyan) and the routing solution (yellow)

2.3 Obstacle detection

To detect obstacles and prevent collisions with customers and other carts, our system incorporates the fusion of camera and LIDAR sensor technology. The sensors are mounted on the cart's front (figure 4). This integration enables the detection of obstacles and their distances from the cart, allowing for real-time path adjustments to avoid collisions. Sensor fusion is used to improve the accuracy and reliability of obstacle detection by combining data from multiple sensors. The LIDAR is suitable for measuring distance and creating a 3D point cloud of the environment, while the camera provides high-resolution images and additional information on object characteristics such as colour and texture. The camera is used to identify and detect the position of the obstacle and calculate the azimuth of the obstacle in the camera coordinate system. Human detection is performed using a ready-made deep learning neural network model, while the cart detection uses a new model developed with transfer learning on the MobilenetSSD architecture as it was described in the previous chapter. Once the obstacle is detected, the azimuth is used by the LIDAR to calculate the average distance from the 3D point-cloud. After the obstacle distance is calculated, it is sent to the cloud platform and it is then communicated to the app. The tablet mounted on the shopping cart displays the cart's trajectory and detected obstacles in real-time, providing warning of obstacles to the user and allowing for a safer shopping experience.

Figure 4. Object detection camera for product identification

3 Results and Limitations

The system was tested in real-life supermarket scenarios to evaluate its accuracy and limitations. The performance of the system was analyzed based on the accuracy of product detection and the overall user experience. Challenges and limitations observed during field tests were documented to guide future improvements. The system achieved an accuracy of approximately 70 % on the product identification task. Limitations were observed in the detection of certain products, particularly those obscured by others in the cart. A solution to this problem is an increase to the training dataset with more images with multiple products in the cart in order to improve the model's detection capabilities. The proposed shortest route estimation and obstacle detection system for the supermarket cart was tested using the supermarket map and the products positions. The simulated annealing TSP algorithm successfully optimized the route for visiting products in the shopping list, significantly reducing the overall distance traveled. The camera and LIDAR sensor fusion technology effectively detected moving obstacles such as people and shopping carts. The tablet mounted on the shopping cart provided users with up-to-date information on the cart's trajectory and detected obstacles, offering valuable assistance to elderly or disabled shoppers who may have difficulties maneuvering the cart.

4 Conclusion

This study demonstrated the potential of deep learning in supermarket shopping with target to facilitate the customer experience. A dataset of images of supermarket products was created and used for training the object detection model for the automatic shopping list fulfilment. Additionally an heuristic algorithm was used for shortest route estimation by modeling the product collection process as a variant of the Traveling Salesman Problem. Furthermore, the integration of camera and LIDAR sensor technology for obstacle detection prevents collisions with customers and other carts. The proposed system holds significant potential for enhancing the supermarket shopping experience, particularly for elderly and disabled shoppers, by improving efficiency, ensuring safety, and offering valuable assistance. Additionally, extensive testing and validation in real-world supermarket settings will be conducted to further assess the system's performance and potential impact on the shopping experience .

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